

A BETTER CHARACTERIZATION OF BIOPHYSICAL PERFORMANCE USING THE TRANSFORMATION MATRIX: THE CASE OF THE PAPER AND PULP INDUSTRY FROM A NEXUS PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Energy intensity and resource productivity are widespread indicators of energy and material intensity in European institutions. However, they present important flaws when used to characterize the factors affecting the energy and material performance of an economy: they neglect the effects of the openness and differences in the structure of the economies. In this study we propose the Transformation Matrix (TM) as an alternative accounting framework based in Multi-Scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) to analyze the energy and material metabolism, including the generation of value added. The TM extend the accounting of the End-use Matrix (EUM) to flows out of human control as water and emissions, which add relevant information about the nexus from a biophysical approach. An example is provided with the analysis of the “Paper, pulp and print” subsector in Europe. Countries specialized in the production of pulp and paper are net exporters with high energy and water metabolic rates. On the contrary, countries importing pulp and paper and producing paper products generate value added with lower energy and water metabolic rates and less GHG per hour of work in the sector.

INTRODUCTION

The European Energy Efficiency Directive and other policies are using energy intensity as an indicator of efficiency to define targets associated with the concept of “improvement”: the lower the better (European Environment Agency, 2018). However, the endorsement of this narrative neglects the implications of three factors affecting energy intensity: (i) outsourcing economic activities, importing rather than producing consumed goods; (ii) the mix of economic activities, which have a broad range of energy intensities; and (iii) multiscale performance entanglements (e.g. Jevons paradox) implying a continuous adjustment of the relative importance of economic activities following changes in technological performance. The same set of problems is found when analysing the resource productivity indicator, a lead indicator used in the resource efficiency scoreboard (European Commission, 2016). The systemic problem faced when simplifying the complexity of energy performance of a social-ecological system into just a single number has been already criticised elsewhere (Fiorito, 2013; Giampietro et al., 2012). In this paper we focus on this very same problem but in relation to the use of the material intensity indicator. In particular, we propose to adopt a method of multiscale integrated assessment to avoid excessive simplification (Giampietro et al., 2013; Velasco-Fernández et al., 2018), also to the analysis of intensity of material products. It also addresses the issue of the openness of the economy: how trade does affect the overall biophysical performance of an economy. Favorable terms of trade can be used to externalize environmental impacts, depletion of resources and requirement of cheap labor to other economies. Addressing the issue of openness requires a biophysical accounting of material flows that distinguishes between raw materials, semi-finished products and final products. Each of these flows of materials must have accounted the quantities that are domestically produced and consumed in the economy and those that are going to and coming from international markets.

ANALYZING THE BIOPHYSICAL PERFORMANCE OF THE ECONOMIC PROCESS ACROSS SCALES

We start the analysis focusing on the limitations of the use of energy and material intensity as indicators of performance using a simplified scheme of the metabolic pattern illustrated in Figure 1. The activities producing raw materials (upper left quadrant), semi-finished products (lower right quadrant) and producing final products (lower left quadrant) are depicted separated from the rest of human activities. This “material sector” is where raw materials (non-energy primary sectors as agriculture, forestry, fishing, mining and quarrying) are exploited to produce final products (secondary sectors

as manufacturing and construction). The final products are then used by the rest of the economic process for expressing its functions. In this figure one can see five factors that influence the material intensity and the environmental impacts associated with the metabolism of a social-ecological system: (i) the degree of openness of the primary sectors; (ii) the mix of raw material, semi-finished and finished products used in society; (iii) the mix of economic activities carried out in the society; (iv) a selective externalization of secondary activities, i.e. import-export of semi-finished and final products; and (v) credit leverage and quantitative easing ('virtual money') boosting the GDP not requiring the production of an equivalent volume of products and services.

If we want to assess the different materials that one country needs to consume in its metabolism and the relative environmental impact, we must identify relevant categories of material flows. In fact, we cannot sum tons of raw materials (e.g. iron ore) and tones of final products using that material (e.g. fridge made of iron in an alloy as steel) under a generic category "iron". The nature of the impossibility of summing quantities of different "matter forms" in kg, is exactly the same as the one faced when trying to sum quantities of different "energy forms" in J. A Joule of coal (a Primary Energy Source) cannot be summed to 1 Joule of electricity (an Energy Carrier). To avoid this problem, current biophysical material indicators based in Material Flow Accounting tend to adopt very generic categories of accounting when mapping the flows coming from the biosphere (the ones produced or extracted by primary sectors), in terms of raw materials equivalents: biomass, metal ores, non-metallic minerals and fossil energy materials. But then, if we want to look at the specific of traded products: "each traded product is assigned to one material category only" (Eurostat, 2017a). This implies summing kg of refrigerator to kg of iron. Needless to say, using monetary quantifications it becomes impossible to analyze technological performances or environmental impacts. Thus, monetary representations are uselessness to characterize the biophysical performance of a social-ecological system (Giampietro et al., 2012). A proper relation between Raw Material, Carriers and End Uses has to be based on the development of grammars – e.g. for water, food, energy and materials – allowing a pertinent accounting of relevant flows across different categories and among them in the nexus (Giampietro, 2018; Giampietro et al., 2014).

Figure 1 : The metabolic pattern of a social-ecological system and the factors affecting its material intensity and environmental

THE PAPER, PULP AND PRINT SUBSECTOR

Data & Methods

The End-use Matrix (EUM) is an accounting framework developed in MuSIASEM tracking the metabolic pattern of energy and material flows controlled by funds under human control. Unlike the End-use Matrix (EUM), the Transformation Matrix (TM) also includes flows out of human control required for expressing a given societal function or end-uses. End-uses (a specific combination of metabolized flows and fund elements required to express a given task) can be defined at different levels and scales and they can be associated with the expression of different social practices. In previous applications, the metabolic pattern of societal systems has been represented in EUMs that include energy carriers, human activity and monetary value-added generation (Velasco-Fernández et al., 2018). In the present work, we introduce two innovations in the accounting using the Transformation Matrix: (i) the consideration of water consumed and emissions generated (CO₂ equivalent), showing how the TM can manage the Nexus at the level of end-uses; and (ii)

the accounting of material products, making possible to distinguish relevant differences among the metabolic patterns inside the same manufacturing subsector and identifying its role in the global market through the physical trade balance. In the expression in Figure 2, we can see the fund, flows and fund-flow ratios considered for each country and for the European region. Namely, the Transformation Matrix (expressed in array-function way) for the analysed subsector. It is defined as a combination of extensive variables - indicating the size of the end-uses - and intensive variables - characterizing the metabolic pattern (or the blueprint) of the fund elements.

Figure 2 Transformation Matrix characterizing the analysis in data array format

Figure 3 shows the set of flows and fund considered in the analysis across different scales. The current analysis just considers European and country scales for one subsector. The other scales represented are just for illustrative purposes of the multiscale characterization. The countries selected for the analysis are 22: 21 members of the European Union and Norway. The non-included EU countries are Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, France, Luxembourg, Malta and Slovenia and they were excluded due to lack of data. Norway is included as it is member of CEPI (Confederation of European Paper Industries) and the European Economic Area.

Figure 3 Flows and fund characterizing the analysis across scales

Data on energy use come from Eurostat Energy Balances (Eurostat, 2018) for the year 2012, which has been chosen because it is the year with least missing data and closer to 2011 (the last available for Exiobase). Energy throughputs are presented in the form of Energy Carriers following the aggregation of energy products presented in the protocol of Velasco-Fernández et al. (2018). Data on hours worked (Human Activity) and Value Added are obtained from Annual detailed enterprise statistics for industry (sbs_na_ind_r2) (Eurostat, 2015) for year 2012 provided by Eurostat (V16150 Number of hours worked by employees for HA and V12150: Value added at factor cost for VA).

The source of data for water and CO_{2eq} come from Exiobase 3.4 satellite accounts for year 2011 (Stadler et al., 2018; Tukker et al., 2013; Wood et al., 2015), being the closer year to 2012 available. In Exiobase there is a larger sector disaggregation than in Eurostat Energy balances, and the following sub-sectors of Paper, pulp and print were available: Pulp; Re-processing of secondary paper into new pulp; Paper; and Publishing, printing and reproduction of recorded media. The water variables are blue water consumption and blue water withdrawal, which were summed for the sub-sectors taking part of Paper, Pulp and Print. CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O variables were taken from the satellite accounts and then multiplied by their corresponding IPCC 100-year time horizon Global Warming Potentials (Houghton and IPCC, 1996) to calculate the CO_{2eq}.

In relation to the material products produced in the Paper, Pulp and Print sector (NACE rev 2 codes 17 and 18), they were obtained from PRODUCTION COMMUNAUTAIRE (PRODCOM) (prom) (Eurostat, 2017b). However, PRODCOM database considers more than 140 categories of products for this subsector. In order to handle this huge amount of data 5 categories of products have been chosen for the year 2012: (i) Pulp (codes beginning in 1711) measured in kg of substance 90 % dry (kg 90% sdt); (ii) Paper & Paperboard (codes beginning in 1712) measured in kg; (iii) Articles of paper and paperboard (codes beginning in 172) measured in kg; (iv) Printing and related services (codes beginning in 181); and 5. Reproduction and recorded material (codes beginning in 182). The variety of products inside these categories varies from 4 items for Pulp to almost 50 items for the Paper & Paperboard. As we can see, at this level of analysis the loss of information due to aggregation of different types of products is important. Nonetheless, their conscious and transparent aggregation makes us aware of the challenges of carrying this type of analysis and understand the lack of availability of methods to carry them out. Additionally, there is a large amount of missing and confidential data in the PRODCOM database. In fact, there is only information for pulp production, then sold production data has been used instead. No data is available for printing and related services, as for reproduction and recorded material.

Results and Discussion

The Transformation Matrix has been applied to study the differences of the subsector “Paper, Pulp & Printing” across European countries (see Table 1). The information space generated in this way includes not only an analysis of energy metabolism (Velasco-Fernández et al., 2018), but also an analysis on other materials characterizing: (i) the level of technical capitalization of the specific sector (Energy Metabolic Rates, EMR_i in MJ per hour of labour); (ii) the level of value added generation (Economic Job Productivities, EJP_i in € per hour of labour); (iii) the expansion to relevant dimensions of the Nexus beyond energy when evaluating the biophysical performance, such as the Water Metabolic Rate and the Emission Production Rate; and (iv) the pace and the mix of products supply (Product Production Rates, PPR_i measured in kg of product produced per hour). The combination of these indicators characterizes the metabolic patterns

of specific economic sectors and subsectors in relation to the different productive processes taking place in them (pulp, paper or paper articles production).

Table 1 The Transformation Matrix of the Paper, Pulp & Print subsector of EU22 for the year 2012

2012																			
Paper, Pulp & Print	HA (Mh/year)	EMR_elec (MJ/h)	EMR_heat (MJ/h)	EMR_fuel (MJ/h)	WMR (l/h)	EJP (€/h)	PPR_pulp (kg90%/h)	PPR_pap (kg/h)	PPR_ppr (kg/h)	EPR (tCO ₂ eq/h)	ET_elec (TJ/year)	ET_heat (TJ/year)	ET_fuel (TJ/year)	WT (t/year)	VA (M€)	PO_pulp (kg 90%)	PO_paper (kg)	PO_ppro (kg)	CO ₂ eq (MtCO ₂ eq)
EU-22	2,023	218	391	15	0.42	34	9.1	25	23	13	427	772	33	856	68	1.3E+10	5.1E+10	4.7E+10	2.6E+04
Austria	49	358	1,040	8.5	0.64	57	18	50	18	25	17	52	0.65	31	2.7	8.9E+08	2.4E+09	8.5E+08	1.2E+03
Belgium	40	279	380	26	1.9	60	-	7.9	36	15	9.5	17	0.44	79	2.2	-	3.2E+08	1.5E+09	6.0E+02
Bulgaria	30	44	256	6.8	0.44	6.3	-	1.1	8.7	4.6	1.2	7.4	0.40	13	0.19	-	3.2E+07	2.6E+08	1.4E+02
Croatia	22	48	101	7.5	0.16	12	1.3	7.2	9.7	6.6	1.2	2.1	0.32	3.6	0.26	3.0E+07	1.6E+08	2.2E+08	1.5E+02
Czech Republic	63	96	280	3.2	0.23	16	-	3.3	14	9.9	6.0	17	0.28	14	1.0	-	2.1E+08	8.6E+08	6.3E+02
Finland	50	1,386	3,095	61	3.8	67	92	211	9.2	58	73	151	3.0	189	3.5	4.6E+09	1.1E+10	4.6E+08	2.9E+03
Germany	458	192	285	5.0	0.13	39	0.17	33	26	15	86	138	2.9	62	17	7.6E+07	1.5E+10	1.2E+10	7.0E+03
Greece	27	72	49	30	0.07	20	0.0	5.6	12	5.9	1.4	1.7	0.72	1.8	0.61	0.0E+00	1.5E+08	3.2E+08	1.6E+02
Hungary	45	47	71	2.8	0.13	13	-	-	12	4.3	2.0	3.1	0.08	5.6	0.54	-	-	5.6E+08	1.9E+02
Ireland	16	55	9.0	6.2	0.52	38	0.0	0.23	17	1.8	0.80	0.20	0.09	8.5	0.52	0.0E+00	3.7E+06	2.7E+08	2.9E+01
Italy	239	142	123	8.8	0.45	36	0.36	27	44	9.1	35	33	1.6	107	8.6	8.7E+07	6.5E+09	1.1E+10	2.2E+03
Latvia	6.6	16	23	0.0	0.31	11	0.0	-	6.5	1.5	0.11	0.21	0.0	2.1	0.068	0.0E+00	-	4.3E+07	9.9E+00
Lithuania	11	38	72	3.6	0.05	12	0.14	9.5	17	5.8	0.58	1.1	0.0	0.61	0.13	1.5E+06	1.1E+08	1.9E+08	6.6E+01
Netherlands	67	140	221	0.0	0.26	47	-	7.0	30	15	9.1	14	0.0	18	3.2	-	4.7E+08	2.0E+09	1.0E+03
Norway	17	968	527	101	3.7	56	-	-	6.4	17	16	14	2.4	63	0.65	1.3E+08	-	1.1E+08	2.8E+02
Poland	171	91	245	11	0.20	18	7.4	5.2	22	9.8	13	35	1.9	34	2.7	1.3E+09	8.9E+08	3.7E+09	1.7E+03
Portugal	50	216	896	43	0.32	26	42	39	20	9.1	11	39	1.3	16	1.3	2.1E+09	2.0E+09	1.0E+09	4.5E+02
Romania	53	25	29	2.1	0.14	6.5	0.0	2.3	9.2	1.5	1.6	1.3	0.0	7.2	0.40	0.0E+00	1.2E+08	4.9E+08	8.0E+01
Slovakia	21	174	538	3.9	1.5	19	-	1.8	8.2	12	3.6	16	0.28	31	0.41	-	3.8E+07	1.7E+08	2.6E+02
Spain	189	107	313	26	0.07	32	7.3	19	27	11	19	44	6.9	12	6.3	1.4E+09	3.6E+09	5.0E+09	2.1E+03
Sweden	79	1,069	2,023	98	1.4	57	58	70	9.8	17	82	158	8.3	108	4.7	4.6E+09	5.5E+09	7.8E+08	1.4E+03
United Kingdom	317	129	88	3.7	0.16	35	0.0	8.5	17	11	39	27	1.2	51	11	0.0E+00	2.7E+09	5.4E+09	3.5E+03

Moreover, when comparing the metabolic pattern of these countries in relation to their upper geographical level (EU-22) we can better understand the differences among them. For example, in the Paper, Pulp and Print sub-sectors of countries like Finland, Norway and Sweden we can see that they are specialized in the pulp and paper production (PPR_pulp & PPR_pap) with a high level of capitalization (EMRs) and high economic productivity (EJP). Portugal is still specialized in the pulp and paper production but with lower capitalization and lower economic job productivity. Additionally, we can see that high-water metabolic rates are related with high EMRs and PPRs (Finland and Norway). However, some exceptions are found as the case of Sweden or Portugal for the lower part, or Belgium with high WMR while low pulp and paper PPRs and EMRs. Similarly it happens with the emission production rate (EPR). While Finland presents the highest EPR, Sweden and Norway show lower than expected. Explaining these issues would require characterizing lower levels for detecting differences in the mix of processes and technologies in each subsector.

When complementing the TM with the pattern of import, export and physical trade balance (Table 2) we can get a deeper understanding of the differences among the metabolic rates and the role of the countries in the global market. For example: Finland, Sweden and Portugal present a physical product trade balance pattern of exporters of Pulp; Italy is a clear importer of pulp and paper for producing paper products to export; Germany imports just pulp and exports paper and paper products; the Netherlands is a clear trader presenting intensive importation and exportation in all products. Looking this last case, one can see how the Economic Energy Intensity (MJ/€) usually used is not an effective indicator of efficiency, even at a disaggregated level as a subsector: Netherlands EEI is 13MJ/€ while it is 106 MJ/€ for Finland. With this indicator one can only suspect that the Netherlands presents a decoupled or dematerialized pattern since it is consuming a low level of energy and materials and generate high level of value added. It is important to be capable to make a distinction between changes in efficiency due to improved process of transformation and due to the shifting of biophysical costs to other Social-Ecological Systems.

Table 2 Export, Import and Physical products trade balance for EU22 countries, year 2012

2012	Export			Import			Physical Products Trade Balance		
Paper, Pulp and Print	Paper pulp (kg 90% sdt)	Paper & paperboard (kg)	Paper & paperboard products (kg)	Paper pulp (kg 90% sdt)	Paper & paperboard (kg)	Paper & paperboard products (kg)	Paper pulp (kg 90% sdt)	Paper & paperboard (kg)	Paper & paperboard products (kg)
Austria	3,8E+08	4,2E+9	5,3E+8	6,8E+08	1,4E+9	4,7E+8	-3,0E+08	2,7E+09	6,8E+07
Belgium	8,5E+08	3,5E+9	8,6E+8	1,0E+09	4,1E+9	8,4E+8	-1,4E+08	-5,9E+08	1,7E+07
Bulgaria	8,0E+07	1,2E+8	3,3E+7	2,1E+07	3,0E+8	7,0E+7	5,9E+07	-1,7E+08	-3,7E+07
Croatia	0,0E+00	1,3E+8	7,2E+7	1,0E+05	2,9E+8	8,1E+7	-1,0E+05	-1,6E+08	-9,4E+06
Czech Republic	3,6E+08	6,7E+8	5,1E+8	1,6E+08	1,3E+9	4,7E+8	2,0E+08	-5,9E+08	4,0E+07
Finland	2,5E+09	8,9E+9	2,0E+8	4,9E+08	4,8E+8	9,5E+7	2,0E+09	8,4E+09	1,0E+08
Germany	1,0E+09	1,4E+10	3,0E+9	4,4E+09	1,1E+10	1,6E+9	-3,4E+09	2,8E+09	1,4E+09
Greece	1,2E+07	9,1E+7	5,2E+7	9,8E+07	6,0E+8	1,4E+8	-8,6E+07	-5,1E+08	-8,5E+07
Hungary	4,4E+06	6,1E+8	2,2E+8	9,4E+07	7,8E+8	2,5E+8	-9,0E+07	-1,7E+08	-2,3E+07
Ireland	0,0E+00	2,3E+7	9,7E+7	3,9E+07	3,9E+8	2,4E+8	-3,9E+07	-3,6E+08	-1,4E+08
Italy	9,8E+06	3,4E+9	1,3E+9	2,9E+09	5,0E+9	3,4E+8	-2,9E+09	-1,6E+09	1,0E+09
Latvia	8,3E+06	3,3E+7	5,9E+7	9,3E+06	1,7E+8	5,2E+7	-1,0E+06	-1,4E+08	7,4E+06
Lithuania	3,8E+07	1,3E+8	1,0E+8	4,9E+07	2,3E+8	1,3E+8	-1,2E+07	-1,1E+08	-2,9E+07
Netherlands	2,2E+09	2,5E+9	8,7E+8	2,7E+09	2,6E+9	9,7E+8	-5,3E+08	-1,0E+08	-9,9E+07
Norway	0,0E+00	0,0E+0	0,0E+0	0,0E+00	0,0E+0	0,0E+0	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Poland	1,7E+07	2,2E+9	1,1E+9	6,4E+08	3,4E+9	4,2E+8	-6,2E+08	-1,1E+09	6,7E+08
Portugal	1,1E+09	1,8E+9	1,8E+8	9,1E+07	8,3E+8	1,8E+8	9,8E+08	9,7E+08	-6,2E+05
Romania	7,8E+05	1,0E+8	6,6E+7	7,4E+07	5,6E+8	1,7E+8	-7,3E+07	-4,6E+08	-1,1E+08
Slovakia	1,9E+08	6,5E+8	2,4E+8	1,2E+08	4,0E+8	2,3E+8	7,8E+07	2,4E+08	9,6E+06
Spain	1,1E+09	3,0E+9	7,4E+8	8,6E+08	2,9E+9	5,2E+8	2,1E+08	1,0E+08	2,3E+08
Sweden	3,0E+09	1,1E+10	4,4E+8	4,8E+08	9,4E+8	3,5E+8	2,6E+09	9,6E+09	8,9E+07
United Kingdom	8,9E+06	1,4E+9	4,5E+8	9,1E+08	6,2E+9	1,0E+9	-9,0E+08	-4,8E+09	-5,7E+08

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

This work presents an innovative accounting framework to characterize the biophysical performance of subsectors that can represent an effective analytical tool to inform policy. The Transformation Matrix to the analysis of material products makes it still possible to identify how different forms of energy carriers (electricity, fuels and process heat) are used to perform different societal tasks: who is using them, how much of them, and how. Adding the non-energy products provides a better analysis of “what is done” in the different elements of the End-use Matrix, expanding the analysis to other relevant elements of the nexus as water and emissions. In this way, the analysis of local biophysical constraints (limiting the production) can be linked to an analysis of the implications of externalization (dependence on imports) to see what countries are producing *what*, for *whom* and *how*. Therefore, this approach improves the quality of the information currently used to discuss environmental and trade agreements.

It should be noted that this analysis presents all its potentiality when considered its quantitative connections with upper levels (sector, paid work and whole society) presented in previous works (Giampietro et al., 2017; Velasco-Fernández et al., 2018). MuSIASEM accounting relates macroeconomic biophysical accounting to lower levels and to other dimensions relevant for the nexus, such as water, emissions or materials, which affect ecosystems and the sustainability of modern societies. The integration of biophysical and monetary analysis is crucial for generating relevant information for the governance of the nexus and other sustainability issues.

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